

Reality of Women in Indonesian Society: A Feminism Approach

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ABSTRACT: Issues regarding gender in Indonesia are still ongoing, which cannot be denied that the patriarchal system is still very strong. Feminist law is based on feminist sociology, feminist philosophy and feminist history expansion of women's attention later in life. At the end of the 20th century, there were many feminist movements seen as a splinter of the Critical Legal Studies movement, of which there are many in essence provides criticism of the legal logic that has been used, its manipulative nature and legal dependence on politics, economics, the role of law in forming patterns social relations, and the formation of hierarchies by legal provisions is not fundamental. Feminist theories often ignore women's contemporary position, focusing on women historical past or utopian future. Focus on praxis often about creating revolutions, egalitarian reforms, or cultural utopias. Much of sociology is based on what are known as individual relationships with the world as it is and as it is maintained.

KEYWORD: gender, patriarchy, feminism, inequality.

INTRODUCTION

We cannot deny that from some time ago until now issues regarding gender are still circulating. This is due to the perspective of the people themselves. Moreover, the culture in our country includes various races and religions. And this is what causes the viewpoints in each society to be different, especially in terms of views regarding gender. As we know, our society adheres to a patriarchal system where men are seen as the most powerful gender compared to women. On the other hand, women are a weaker gender when compared to men.

There are many assumptions and even behaviours in our society that form a social construction that men have high standards to be recognized as men, such as men must be more dominant than women in all things, including work, education, opportunities and politics. On the other hand, this becomes unusual if women are in positions that can exceed men. This makes women have to submit to men, and even causes oppression of women in all aspects of life.

Feminism is an ideology or the demanding women's movement emancipation or equality and justice of rights man with woman. Feminism originates from Latin, femina or woman. This term came into use in the 1890s, refers to the theory of equality of men and women and the movement for gain women's rights. Now this is international literature defines it as differentiation on the basis of women's rights on equality of women and men.

Starting from the assumption that people women experience discrimination and exploitation where they really struggling to stop this discrimination. In that sense, actually feminists don't have to be women, and may be a Muslim or a Muslim at. Problems arise when they try answering people's 'why' questions women are discriminated against or treated unfair? This is what causes it feminism was born and developed rapidly, especially among women.

The feminist movement began at the end of the century 18th, but ending 20th century, sound Women in the legal field, especially theory law, emerge and mean. Feminist law which is based on feminist sociology, philosophy feminism and feminist history are expansion of women's attention later in life. At the end of the 20th century, there were many feminist movements seen as a splinter of the Critical movement Legal Studies, which is basically a lot provides criticism of legal logic during this use, manipulative nature and dependence of law on politics, economics, the role of law in shaping patterns of social relationships, and formation hierarchy by legal provisions fundamental.

Indonesian feminism refers on the feminist movement in Indonesia develop in a cultural context and Indonesian social. This movement focuses in efforts to achieve equality gender and fighting discrimination towards women in Indonesia. History of the feminist movement in

Indonesia began in 1912 when Raden Ajeng Kartini, a leading female figure in Java during the Dutch colonial period, writing a series of letters about rights women and gender equality. After Indonesian independence in In 1945, the feminist movement grew developed with its founding women's organizations such as the Indonesian Women's Movement and Indonesian Women's Congress (Darwin, 2004).

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However, the feminist movement in Indonesia is experiencing internal challenges fighting for gender equality in amidst a strong patriarchal culture and conservative. Several issues arise focus of the feminist movement in Indonesia including sexual violence, discrimination in education and employment, and protection of rights female reproduction.

Nonetheless, movement feminism in Indonesia continues to grow and developed with its founding various organizations and groups women's advocacy. Some in among them is the Women's Coalition Indonesia for Justice and Democracy, Mahardhika Women, and the Indonesian Migrant Workers Union. The feminist movement in Indonesia too increasingly connected to movement global feminism through internet access and social media. Although inspired, but has cultural characteristics and context typical. One of the characteristics of feminism Indonesia is focused on issues specific to the social context, Indonesian economy and politics, such as violence against women, discrimination in the workplace, and disparities in access to education and health.

Over the last few decades, the Indonesian feminist movement has achieved a number of victories important. For example, in some recent years, the feminist movement has successfully fought for change more legal regulations protect women's rights, such as law on violence in the household and protection child.

Nevertheless, movement Indonesian feminism still facing many challenges and complex struggle. Asn example of the problem with religious law. So it is necessary hard work and patience as reinforcement efforts to change patterns people's thoughts and actions Indonesia still considers it women as creatures weak and inferior.

METHOD

This research uses literature review method. In this study, researchers looked for and collect information from various sources sources such as books, scientific journals, papers, research reports, and other sources relevant to research topic. Next, researchers analyze literature, then process it research material becomes a study literature. This method provides researchers with relevant information and can help in identify research gaps and an area that needs further research. In a study conducted by (Marzali, 2017) Literature review is a digging and tracing library by reviewing various journals, books and other publications related to the research title, for create a study.

DISCUSSION

Feminist Thought

Feminism is a social movement and politics aimed at achieve gender equality in all aspects of life (Ilaa, 2021). Feminist thinking highlights and against gender inequality exist in society and culture.

There are several schools or types feminist thought that has developed over several decades Lastly, among others (Retnani, 2017):

- a. Liberal Feminism: Trends This feminism focuses on effort to achieve equality gender through legal reform and public policy. They believes in gender equality can be achieved through improvements existing systems and institutions.
- b. Radical Feminism: This feminism considers that gender inequality is not it just happens because it is discrimination in public institutions, but also in private institutions such as family and relationships interpersonal. Therefore, they think that social revolution is necessary for achieve gender equality.
- c. Marxist Feminism: This feminism emphasizes the importance of social class within struggle to achieve gender equality. They believe that capitalism and patriarchy is interrelated and that both must be abolished in order gender equality can be achieved.
- d. Intersectional Feminism: This feminism emphasizes that gender inequality is not apart from discrimination based on social class, race, sexuality, religion, and so on. Therefore, they proposed an approach who considers intersection between various forms This discrimination is deep struggle to achieve gender equality.

Feminist thinking continues develop and develop within respond to changes in society and culture. However, the goal remains the same, namely to achieve gender equality and end all forms of injustice gender. This thought originates from belief that women experiencing injustice and discrimination in various aspects life because of their gender (Suhada, 2021). Some concepts important in feminist thought includes:

- a. Gender Equality: Feminism emphasize its importance gender equality between women and men. This involves efforts to eliminate gender discrimination in terms of education, employment, income, political rights, and access to other resources.
- b. Patriarchy: Patriarchy is a system social that provides power and control over men and ignore or oppress women. Feminism against patriarchy and demanding gender equality in the whole society.
- c. Gender Identity: Feminism recognize that gender identity is a social construct varies from time to time and culture to culture. As as a result, feminism is opposed gender stereotypes restrict women in certain roles and emphasize its importance recognition and awards to various identities gender.
- d. Choice: Feminism emphasizes the importance of women's choices in terms of personal life and professional. It's involving remove that obstacle hinder women from entering make decisions and determine the course of their lives Alone.
- e. Awareness: Awareness (or critical awareness) is a process in which the individual questions their own beliefs and their society. Feminism emphasizes its importance inner awareness identify and overcome gender inequality.

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f. Solidarity: Solidarity refers on a sense of unity and support among women in the feminist movement. Feminism emphasizes the importance of solidarity between women in resistance gender inequality and fighting for equality gender.

History of the Emergence of Feminism in Indonesia

Feminism in Indonesia emerged along with development nationalism at the beginning of the 20th century, when women started getting involved in independence movement and social politics. One of the early figures feminism in Indonesia is Kartini, which encourages women to get the same rights with men through education. In 1912, female first time forming an organization feminists in Indonesia, namely Indische Vrouwenbond (IVB), which aims to improve welfare women and fight for their rights. IVB is then followed by other feminist organizations such as the Women's Emancipation Association Indonesia (PEWI) and the Women's Movement Awake (GWS) (Hidayati Djoeffan, 2001).

Meanwhile during the period Japanese occupation of Indonesia in World War II, Indonesian women were active involved in the struggle independence. After Indonesia independence in 1945, movement feminism began to develop rapidly. In 1947, an organization called the Indonesian Association Women (PIP) was founded. Organization it has a broader purpose than feminist organizations previously, namely to fight for women's rights and also to fight for it Indonesian independence (Syakwan, 2006). But after independence Indonesia, the feminist movement in fact experienced setbacks, this is because a government priority that remains focused on national development. Apart from that, the emergence of people who opposed the feminist movement because they feel that this movement threaten traditions and values already available. Some people even trying to fight the feminist movement and organize movements counter feminists, like the movement masculinism (Ira Larasati, 2017).

It was only in the 1980s, the feminist movement began to revive in Indonesia with a focus on struggle for women's rights such as rights to the body and economic rights. Several feminist organizations appeared at that time was Solidarity Women, Journal Foundation Women, and the Women's Coalition Indonesia (Aripurnami, 2013). Until Currently, the feminist movement continues growing in Indonesia and continuing fighting for women's rights. Several issues are in focus feminist struggle in Indonesia today including violence against women, gender discrimination, and equality of rights.

Since then, the feminist movement in Indonesia continues to develop and gave birth to many organizations and women activists who fighting for women's rights, including the right to participate in politics, get education, and the right to work. However, the feminist movement in Indonesia also faces challenges and controversy, especially in matters different views on issues such as reproductive rights and LGBT.

CONCLUSION

Feminism is a social movement and fighting politics Ngender equality and advocating women's rights. This movement has existed since the beginning of the 20th century in Indonesia, and continues to develop over time. Several well-known financial figures in Indonesia, including Kartini, Martha Christina Tiahahu, and Maria Ulfah Santoso. They fight for it women's rights such as rights education and health, as well fighting gender discrimination. In the era modern, feminist movement in Indonesia has developed into various currents such as liberal feminism, and critical feminism. Despite this movement Feminism also faces challenges like gender stereotypes still exist embedded in culture, society the patriarchy, as well as discrimination and violence against women. By therefore, the feminist movement exists in the struggle to achieve equalitygender and justice for women in Indonesia.

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